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Word Formation of Linguistic Landscapes among Small Businesses

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Abstract

This study mainly focused on sociolinguistics, linguistic landscape (LL), and word formation. Methodically, this study materialized the photographed images used to describe this study's research. It denoted that LLs in General Santos manifested as being utilized in business sectors particularly in marketing and advertising. Various word formations were analyzed, such as misspelling, coining, compounding, and inflection. Results showed that misspellings are evident among the LLs and English is the widely used language among the selected LLs.

Keywords: *linguistic landscape, word formation*

Introduction

The era of the 21st century became a facet involving every individual to process interference and interpret an array of cultures and traditions. Linguistics has manifested changes among Filipinos who have been finding a way to communicate effectively. The number of morphological and syntactic structures is immensely manifested in public information. Through this, the newly-coined alien words provided a chance to form an expression of language. Using English slang and jargon is imminent on every billboard, signage, announcement board, social media post, and even formal communication. Finegan (2015) opined that morphological changes are prevalent among teenagers and college students.

Signs disseminate general public-interest messages such as topographic information, directions, warnings, etc. Public signs also appear in commercial contexts like marketing and advertising, drawing attention to a business or product (Backhaus, 2017). Public signs are semiotic signs that also stand for something other than themselves. Thus, a public sign is a signifier that relates to a signified, such as a company, a product, a place, a rule, or some other concept. On the other hand, a sign indicates a direction on how to get to a place, as in the case of guidance signs, or call attention to it, as advertisement signs do. McCarthy (2002) stated that word formation in the linguistic landscape (LL), word formation in morphology study has many processes, such as derivation, compound, blending, acronym, initialism, inflection, borrowing, coinage, conversion, clipping, back-formation, and onomatopoeia.

The utilization of English worldwide is a mark of globalization defined in economic terms of markets, production, and consumption. Using English in businesses is aimed at increasing their sales, and thus, its presence is motivated by economic reasons. English also raises the issue of identity and power and thus can have consequences for the balance between the different languages in multilingual situations. Hence, General Santos manifested the same agony in linguistic landscapes - where various people misuse LL.

Research Questions

This study determined the word formation utilization of LLs among small business, which is evident in General Santos. This led to answer to the following:

1. What are the types of LL imminent among small business?
2. What word formation is evident in the selected landscapes?
3. What is the common type of word formation evident among LLs?

Literature Review

Ben-Rafael et al. (2009) opined that linguistic landscape research is concerned with using written language in the public sphere. They further defined the linguistic landscape as any sign or announcement located outside or inside a public institution or a private business in a given geographical location. LL has two functions: informative and symbolic. Informative function indicates the borders of the territory of the linguistic group. It showed a specific language or language for communication or to sell products.

On the other hand, the symbolic function refers to the value and status of the languages as perceived by the members of a language group compared to other languages (Cenoz & Gorter, 2009). The presence or absence of languages in public space communicates symbolic messages about the importance, power, significance, and relevance of specific languages or the irrelevance of others (Shohamy, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

The study shall be purely descriptive since it described the imminent LL in the city and the role of English among the LL. The utilization of textual analyses was materialized. A descriptive study determined and reported the way things are. Descriptive research describes events, phenomena, or facts and systematically deals with specific areas or populations.

Procedure

LL analysis relied on visual and photographic analyses. The legal basis of gathering data was engaged in photography, which carefully documented the selected landscapes with irregular word formation among small businesses. After the LLs were photographed, the researchers identified imminent LLs. This was followed by classifying the words morphologically to process the word formation applied in each LL. Then, the common types of word formation used in small businesses were analyzed. Lastly, the distribution of language was determined. LLs were taken from the signage. The presence or absence of languages in small businesses communicates symbolic messages about the importance, power, significance, and relevance of specific languages or the irrelevance of others (Shohamy, 2019). The researchers focused on the language use patterns among small businesses of General Santos.

Data Analysis

Each photographed LL was analyzed by identifying the word formation. These include signage like direction, graffiti, marketing, and advertising. By interpreting quantitative data, the researcher analyzed LL word formation expressed through language choices, official or unofficial signage power dynamics, and hidden agendas represented by disparities between language policies and realities of daily language use.

The researchers focused on determining the imminent types of LL. The LL analysis mainly focused on word formation in morphology namely derivation, compound, blending, acronym and initialism, inflection, borrowing, conversion, clipping, and back formation. Lastly, the LLs shall also be analyzed based on their language distribution.

The utilization of frequency and percentage was emphasized to describe the imminent LL, type of word formation, and language distribution. Thus, rank was used to identify the most common word formation on the selected LLs. The word formation was analyzed by identifying morphological role of each word such as coining, inflection, spelling, and compounding. In conducting this LL analysis, the choice of sampling domain is driven by the study's purpose—a neighborhood selection to reflect the diversity and variations of the communities described (Ban-Raphael, 2006).

Results and Discussion

After gathering the LLs in General Santos, this section presents the word formations found on the LLs.

Table 1. *Linguistic Landscapes Imminent among Small Businesses*

<i>LL</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Directions	2	3.3
Warning Signs	4	6.7
Graffiti	8	13.3
Marketing and Advertising	46	76.7
Total	60	100

The LLs identified in the table above were known to be imminent and evident in General Santos. The city's people have been utilizing LLs for marketing and advertising, which accounts for 76.7% of the total LL. Looking at the presented results above, LL of direction got the lowest percentage (3.3%). LL of warning signs followed this with 6.7% and LL of graffiti with 13.3%. The results showed that LL is mainly used in marketing and advertising in General Santos. The inescapable use of English in advertising, trade, business, and everyday life is explained by the need to suit the needs and expectations of the target audience, particularly the younger generation. However, promoting and preserving the local tongue must and will continue (Takhtarova et al., 2015).

Table 2. *Coining Word Formation in Linguistic Landscape*

<i>Word/Phrase</i>	<i>Process of Word Formation</i>		<i>Type of Word Formation</i>
instaWashers	Instagram (N)	washers (N)	Coining
Milkittea	Milky (Adj)	kitty (Adj) tea (N)	
TwenTea8	Twenty (Adj)	tea (N) eat (N)	
Gazz	Gas (N)	zz (Suffix)	
Starbutts	Star (Adj)	Butts (S)	

Coined words are innovative words that create new semantics. The table above shows the different LLs, processes, and types. The first LL instaWashers can be denoted that came from Instagram and Washers. Instagram is a noun described as a social media application, and Washers refers to the machine used for washing clothes described as a noun.

The second LL is Milkittea, derived from milky, kitty, and tea. Milky is an adjective describing the type of milk used in mixing a tea. Kitty is an adjective that refers to the cat and the business theme. Tea is a noun referring to a beverage composed of leaves and roots.

The third LL is TwenTea8. It is derived from twenty, tea, and eat. Twenty is an adjective referring to the number of seats available in their business. Tea is a noun referring to the beverage they sell - an emphasis that they only offer beverages. Eat is a noun describing the service that the business is offering.

The fourth LL is Gazz, which is derived from gas and zz. Gas is a noun that refers to the product the business offers, denoting the exact meaning of the clipped word gasoline, gas. Zz is a suffix manifested as substituting s for z and an additional z.

The last LL is Starbutts which is derived from star and butts. Star is a noun used as one of the semiotics in business logo. Butts is a noun referring to the buttocks. It was coined from the famous coffee chain Starbucks. Coining creates a new word formation that allows an individual to form a new word based on the preexisting morpheme.

Table 3. *Inflection Word Formation in Linguistic Landscape*

Word/ Phrase	Process of Word Formation		Type of Word Formation
Cokes 4 Sale	Coke (free morpheme) (N)	s (inflectional morpheme)	Inflection
Olengs 4 sell	Uling (free morpheme) (N)	s (inflectional morpheme)	

The table above shows the inflection manifested in the selected LLs in small businesses. Where coke has an inflection, s. Coke is referred to as a free morpheme and is described as a noun, which is a non-alcoholic beverage drink. Oleng is originally spelled Uling, a free morpheme described as a noun which is a charred wood and coconut shell. Both have inflectional morpheme, s, added to form the plural form of the word. Inflection is a morpheme that changes the word's form from singular to plural. In the English language, there are eight inflections, and all are suffixes.

Table 4. *Spelling Word Formation in Linguistic Landscape*

Word/ Phrase	Process of Word Formation				Type of Word Formation	
	Original	Correct Spelling	Original	Correct Spelling	Original	Correct Spelling
Olengs 4 sell	Olengs	Uling	4	for	Sell	Sale
Spes 4 rint	Spes	Space	4	for	Rint	Rent
Stoll Owner	Stoll	Stall				
Casalo for Sale	Casalo	Kasalo				
Jogeng Pants	Jogeng	Jogging				
Ginadili and pagtuway sa manga hayop diri	and	ang	pagtuway	pagtugway	manga	mga

Mispronunciation will lead to misinterpretation, as reading is the most powerful tool in understanding a specific lexicon. It is observed that misspellings manifested as one of the irregularities among the LLs. Where Olengs 4 sell LL is observed to misspell all the words in the phrase. Olengs originated from Hiligaynon. It should be correctly spelled Uling. 4 originated from an English conjunction for. Sell originated from the English word sale, which means selling merchandise or product.

In the same manner, Spes 4 rint LL is observed to misspell all the words. Spes originated from the English word space, which means area, room, apartment, or bed. Similarly, 4 is misspelled with the same reason on the first signage. Rint originated from the English word rent, which means to use a specific place or thing to pay its corresponding amount.

Stoll Owner LL manifested a misspelled word at the beginning of the phrase. Stoll originated from the German stolle, a scaffolding in a building or tunnel. The correct term that should be used is stall since it refers to a cart in a particular area.

Casalo for Sale LL is observed to misspell the beginning word of the phrase. Casalo originated from the Spanish word casalo, which means to eat together or with someone. On the other hand, casalo in the LL means the size of the bottled beverage, which measures 750ml.

Jogeng Pants LL is observed to misspell the start of the phrase. Jogeng originated from the English word jogging, which functioned as an adjective modifying the word pants.

Ginadili and pagtuway sa manga hayop diri LL is observed with three misspellings. The word and should be spelled ang. Pagtuway should be spelled pagtugway, which means to herd. Manga should be spelled mga, meaning a plural marker of the preceding noun. These misspellings (and, pagtuway, manga) manifested because the LL was printed on white paper medium, which can result from the auto-correct function of the software used to prepare the LL.

This is denoted by the fact that the homophone is the reason for the exchange of word usage. The acoustic characteristics of Cebuano speech, including soft and hard pronunciation of sounds, led to mispronouncing the word (Rubino, 2013). Also, the inability to proofread the LL manifested because the seller considered it sufficient. Spelling is a skill best acquired within the framework of learning to write, given that all the words to be studied are necessary for each individual's writing (Croft, 2017). It is compelling for educators to focus on spelling since it has been used in various areas of life skill learning. Proper spelling ensures clear communication, professionalism, and credibility among the LLs and all forms of written communication.

Compounding is producing words by combining two or more classes of words to generate a new shape and meaning. Table 5 showed there were LLs denoted combining one or more classes of words. Where a phonologically spelled phrase was used. Kustomayz Printz LL is a generated phrase from the word customize and prints.

Table 5. *Compound Word Formation in Linguistic Landscape*

<i>Word/ Phrase</i>	<i>Process of Word Formation</i>	<i>Type of Word Formation</i>
Kustomayz Printz	Customize (V)	Prints (N)
Ice Candy	Ice (Adj)	Candy (N)
Milktea	Milk (Adj)	Tea (N)

Customize functions as verb modifying the noun prints. Ice candy LL is a new shape word formation from the words ice and candy. Ice functions as an adjective modifying the noun candy. Milktea LL comes from the words milk and tea. Milk functions as an adjective modifying the noun tea. Compounding can come in different forms - open, closed, and hyphenated.

Table 6. *Common Type of Word Formation on the Selected Linguistic Landscape*

<i>Word Formation</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Compounding	3	3
Spelling	6	1
Inflection	2	4
Coining	5	2

After the data were collected, the table above showed that among the selected LLs, misspelling occurred most among the word formations, followed by coining on the second rank, then compounding on the third, and inflection on the last among the LLs. In order to adequately express and establish written communication, spelling should be improved to convey the intended meaning accurately, making complex text easy to understand and avoid confusion.

Table 7. *Language Distribution of Linguistic Landscapes*

<i>Languages</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
English only	45	75
Filipino only	5	8.3
Cebuano only	5	8.3
Tagalog and English	3	5
English and Cebuano	2	3.4
Total	60	100

Table 7 shows the language utilized in LLs in General Santos, where English is the mainly used language with 75%, followed by Filipino and Cebuano, both garnered 8.3%, then the combination of Tagalog and English with 5%, and English and Cebuano with 3.4%. It was noted that the English language is widely used among signage worldwide, not just in major cities but also in provincial towns and villages. The use of English also involves concerns of identity and power, which can affect the balance of languages in multilingual circumstances. On that note, English is affiliated with ideals such as the global orientation of modernity, success, sophistication, and enjoyment (Piller, 2016). As a bilingual country, the Philippines has been utilizing English, making Filipinos try their best to apply it daily. Also, Filipinos consider English a powerful language, making them think that once English is used, one would sound brighter than those who do not use it. Even Tagalog is not widely used since it lacks power and sophistication, which has been manifested among the LLs.

Conclusions

LLs are widely used in marketing and advertising. Misspelling, coining, compounding, and inflections were manifested among the LLs in General Santos. It was also evident that misspelling is the most common type of word formation among LLs, and English is the most common language used among the LLs in the city. Spelling brought much attention to this study. This was also one of the results of mispronunciation among Filipinos. The prominent use of the English language among LLs is denoted by the fact that the people of General Santos opt to use powerful and sophisticated language to entice their clients and increase market value.

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